

DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY COEFFICIENT OF THE NEW DARGOM CANAL THROUGH FIELD MEASUREMENTS

Jurayev Bakhrom Bakhridinovich

Head of Laboratory (PhD) at the Samarkand Regional Center of the Scientific
Research Institute of Irrigation and Water Problems

Turayev Shamshiddin Jurakulovich

Director of the Samarkand Regional Center of the Scientific Research Institute of
Irrigation and Water Problems. independent researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16779034>

Abstract

In this article, the efficiency coefficient of the Yangi Dargom Canal, which draws water from the left tributary of the Zarafshan River, was determined using generally accepted hydraulic laws and the hydrometric method. The water discharge of the branches receiving water from the canal was calculated and the results were compared.

The main purpose of measuring water consumption is to achieve efficient water use in response to climate change in our region and the reduction of water resources in sources due to anthropogenic factors. This is accomplished through knowing water flow rates, which enables the development of water balance programs along major rivers, canals, and internal networks during low-water years.

Keywords: Water discharge, flow velocity, canal, gauging station, branch.

Introduction. Comprehensive measures have been implemented in the agriculture sector of our republic aimed at conserving water resources, ensuring their rational and efficient use, including maintaining reliable operation of irrigation systems, and significant results have been achieved. The Dargom Canal provides water to 67.5 thousand hectares of land in Samarkand region and 50 thousand hectares in Kashkadarya region. The annual flow volume amounts to 0.9-1.2 km³. The functioning of 562 km of inter-farm and intra-farm canals and 412 hydraulic structures in the Dargom irrigation system depends on the technical condition of the Dargom Canal.

In recent years, intense erosion processes occurring in the canal bed have resulted in the collapse of canal banks, siltation of the channel, and consequently, a decrease in water carrying capacity, leading to a decline in the canal's efficiency. The primary cause of this is the high flow velocity due to the canal's steep longitudinal slope (average slope of 0.004). Instances have been observed where the progression of these channel processes has had negative impacts, potentially leading to emergency situations. However, the high kinetic energy of the flow also presents an opportunity for positive utilization of this condition.

Research subject: Water for the Yangi and Aylanma Dargom canals is drawn from the left-bank tributary of the Ravotkhoja hydroelectric complex built on the Zarafshan River. The Yangi Dargom canal is 10.2 km long and is fully lined with concrete. The canal is equipped with 10 water intake branches and a hydrological station.

Figure 1. The river water intake section of the canal

The climate of the canal area is highly variable, characterized by relatively dry, hot summers and cold winters. Annual precipitation amounts to 329 mm. The air in the region is dry with high evaporation rates (1135 mm). During summer, the absolute maximum air temperature reaches +38-40°C, while in winter, the minimum temperature drops to -26-30°C, with an average annual temperature of +12°C. The period of highest precipitation occurs from October to March, accounting for more than 75% of the annual amount. The area predominantly experiences winds from the northeast and north directions.

The technical condition of the structures. All structures in the Dargom Canal are inspected after the vegetation period, during the autumn and spring seasons. The following observations are conducted to assess the condition of structures and equipment in the canal: water levels in the upper and lower reaches of structures, silt accumulation along the canal route in the upper reaches and erosion of the bottom and banks in the lower reaches, the impact of water flow on the condition of structures, monitoring of areas prone to damage and potential accidents, and filtration from structures and the canal. During the monitoring process, malfunctions in the structures are identified and measures to eliminate them are determined.

Observations are conducted using visual or geodetic methods and other equipment. After a distance of 11 km from the main structure of New Dargom, the canals in this zone merge and flow into Old Dargom. The length is 10.5 km, with a

water discharge of 125 m³/s, and a total elevation drop of 55 m along its slope. There is a 600-meter tunnel along the canal route. The water energy generated from the steep slope is dissipated by 1 rapid-flow spillway and 13 stepped spillways (cascades).

Натижалар ва мулоҳаза: Currently, the determination of the efficiency coefficient along the sections and length of the Yangi Dargom Canal is carried out primarily using the hydrometric method. In this method, a specific section of the canal is selected to determine its efficiency. Within the chosen section, the locations of the upper and lower cross-sections are identified, and the water discharge is measured using hydrometric instruments. The length of the selected section (segment) is determined by the following formula:

$$L=67,4P_i / \sigma \sqrt{n}P \quad (1.1)$$

Here, L represents the length of the selected section in km; P_i denotes the accuracy of water flow measurements in %; P indicates the accuracy of determining water loss in %; σ represents the water loss per 1 km of canal length (expressed as a percentage of water flow); and n is the number of measurements.

After measuring the water discharge in the upper reach, the water discharges of the water intake and canal outlets in the lower reach are measured. The time it takes for water to travel from the upper cross-section to the lower cross-section is determined using the following formula:

$$T=L/60 V_{av} \quad (1.2)$$

The water loss between the selected sections is determined by the following formula:

$$S=Q_{hh} - \sum Q_{ga} + \sum Q_{wd} - Q_{low} \quad (1.3)$$

where: S - value of water loss in the selected section, m³/s; Q_{yuqor} and Q_{past} - water discharges measured in the upper and lower reaches, m³/s; ∑Q_{ar} - the sum of water discharges of all water intake ditches between the sections, m³/s; ∑Q_{tash} - the sum of water discharges discharged into the canal between sections, m³/s.

After determining the absolute value of water loss in the selected section, the relative losses for each kilometer of length are calculated using the following formula:

$$S1=1000S/L \quad \text{l/s 1 км} \quad (1.4)$$

The percentage of water loss per 1 km of length, relative to the average water discharge of the measured cross-sections, is determined using the following formula.

$$\sigma = 100 S_l / Q_{wd} \quad (1.5)$$

here, $Q_{wd} = (Q_{ga} + Q_{low}) / 2$

The coefficient of efficiency (COE) for the canal section is determined by the following formula:

$$FIK = (Q_{hh} - S) / Q_{hh} \quad (1.6)$$

At the head of the Yangi Dargom canal, the water flow measurement result was $Q=59.25 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, the cross-sectional area in the profile was 35.34 m^2 , the average flow velocity was 1.68 m/s , the maximum velocity was 2.77 m/s , and the width of the water surface measured 18.5 m (Figure 2).

Discharge Measurement Summary										Date Measured: Tuesday, June 24, 2025									
Site Information					Measurement Information														
Site Name		Toyloq tuman			Party		Jurayev B.												
Station Number		Yang Darg'om boshi			Boat/Motor		TB5m												
Location		PK52			Meas. Number		1 o'lchov												
System Information				System Setup				Units											
System Type		RS-S5		Transducer Depth (m)		0.10		Distance		m									
Serial Number		6340		Screening Distance (m)		0.02		Velocity		m/s									
Firmware Version		4.10		Salinity (ppt)		0.0		Area		m ²									
Software Version		4.1		Magnetic Declination (deg)		6.4		Discharge		m ³ /s									
								Temperature		degC									
Discharge Calculation Settings								Discharge Results											
Track Reference		GPS-VTG		Left Method		Sloped Bank		Width (m)		18.486									
Depth Reference		Vertical Beam		Right Method		Sloped Bank		Area (m ²)		35.336									
Coordinate System		ENU		Top Fit Type		Power Fit		Mean Speed (m/s)		1.677									
				Bottom Fit Type		Power Fit		Total Q (m ³ /s)		59.253									
				Start Gauge Height (m)		0.00		Maximum Measured Depth		2.253									
				End Gauge Height (m)		0.00		Maximum Measured Speed		2.772									
Measurement Results																			
Tr	Time		Distance				Mean Vel		Discharge						%				
#	Time	Duration	Temp.	Track	DMG	Width	Area	Boat	Water	Left	Right	Top	Middle	Bottom	Total	MBTotal	Measured		
1	R	9:31:52 AM	0:02:10	17.3	22.89	17.73	18.729	35.493	0.176	1.690	0.29	0.08	6.79	41.35	11.47	59.975	--	68.9	
2	L	9:34:09 AM	0:01:34	16.8	22.25	17.24	18.242	35.179	0.237	1.664	0.27	0.09	6.60	41.00	10.57	58.530	--	70.0	
				Mean	17.0	22.57	17.49	18.486	35.336	0.206	1.677	0.28	0.08	6.70	41.18	11.02	59.253	0.000	69.5
				Std Dev	0.2	0.32	0.24	0.243	0.157	0.030	0.013	0.01	0.01	0.09	0.18	0.45	0.722	0.000	0.5
				COV	0.0	0.014	0.014	0.013	0.004	0.147	0.008	0.043	0.069	0.014	0.004	0.040	0.012	0.000	0.008
Exposure Time: 0:03:44																			
Tr1=20250624093152r.rivr; Tr2=20250624093411r.rivr;																			
Comments																			
Tr1=20250624093152r.rivr - Gavjum; Tr2=20250624093411r.rivr - Gavjum;																			

Figure 2. Measurement results at the Yangi Dargom main hydropost

The water discharge measurement in the lower reach of the Yangi Dargom Canal yielded the following results: flow rate $Q=53.10 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, cross-sectional area of the profile 22.62 m^2 , average flow velocity 2.35 m/s , maximum velocity 3.69 m/s , and water surface width 12.8 m (Figure 3).

Discharge Measurement Summary										Date Measured: Tuesday, June 24, 2025								
Site Information					Measurement Information													
Site Name		Toyloq tumani			Party				Jurayev B.									
Station Number		Yangi Darg'om oxiri			Boat/Motor				TB5m									
Location		PK96+00			Meas. Number				1 o'lchov									
System Information				System Setup						Units								
System Type		RS-S5		Transducer Depth (m)		0.10		Distance		m								
Serial Number		6340		Screening Distance (m)		0.02		Velocity		m/s								
Firmware Version		4.10		Salinity (ppt)		0.0		Area		m2								
Software Version		4.1		Magnetic Declination (deg)		6.4		Discharge		m3/s								
								Temperature		degC								
Discharge Calculation Settings								Discharge Results										
Track Reference		GPS-VTG		Left Method		Sloped Bank		Width (m)		12.810								
Depth Reference		Vertical Beam		Right Method		Sloped Bank		Area (m2)		22.617								
Coordinate System		ENU		Top Fit Type		Power Fit		Mean Speed (m/s)		2.347								
				Bottom Fit Type		Power Fit		Total Q (m3/s)		53.099								
				Start Gauge Height (m)		0.00		Maximum Measured		3.148								
				End Gauge Height (m)		0.00		Depth										
								Maximum Measured		3.693								
								Speed										
Measurement Results																		
Tr	Time			Distance				Mean Vel		Discharge						%		
#	Time	Duration	Temp.	Track	DMG	Width	Area	Boat	Water	Left	Right	Top	Middle	Bottom	Total	MBTotal	Measured	
1	R	10:07:48 AM	0:01:55	17.2	24.97	11.68	12.681	22.097	0.217	2.308	0.00	0.00	6.47	33.99	10.55	51.007	--	66.6
2	L	10:09:49 AM	0:01:27	16.8	15.07	11.94	12.939	23.137	0.173	2.385	0.00	0.18	6.73	35.44	12.84	55.192	--	64.2
			Mean	17.0	20.02	11.81	12.810	22.617	0.195	2.347	0.00	0.09	6.60	34.72	11.69	53.099	0.000	65.4
			Std Dev	0.2	4.95	0.13	0.129	0.520	0.022	0.039	0.00	0.09	0.13	0.72	1.14	2.092	0.000	1.2
			COV	0.0	0.247	0.011	0.010	0.023	0.113	0.016	0.000	1.000	0.020	0.021	0.098	0.039	0.000	0.019
Exposure Time: 0:03:22																		
Tr1=20250624100747r.rivr; Tr2=20250624100950r.rivr;																		
Comments																		
Tr1=20250624100747r.rivr - issiq; Tr2=20250624100950r.rivr - issiq;																		

Figure 3. Measurement results at the hydropost of the lower reach of Yangi Dargom

Water flow measurements were conducted in the branches drawing water from the Yangi Dargom Canal, which falls under the management of the Zarafshan Main System Operation Department. The results obtained are presented in the first table.

The efficiency coefficient of the Yangi Dargom Canal was determined using the hydrometric method based on field measurements over a length of 10.6 km. In this process, an accurate calculation of water discharge in the canal's water intake network was conducted, resulting in the determination of the canal's efficiency coefficient to be 0.92 (Table 1). It was found that while the canal's

efficiency coefficient was previously considered to be 0.99, water losses have been increasing due to the deterioration of the canal's concrete lining (Figure 4).

Table 1. Water flow calculations for branches drawing water from the Yangi Darg'om Canal of the Zarafshon Main System Operation Department

№	Name of hydropost or network	Installed PC	Length of water intake network, km	13.08.2024 annual water flow rate	Border water flow measuring station
	The Head of New Darg'om				59.253
1	Elpak-1		0.10	0.05	
2	Rakhmatabad		0.10	0.08	
3	New ditch		0.50	0.30	
4	Elpak 3		0.10	0.05	
5	Boiler ditch		1.00	0.25	
6	Irrigation ditch		0.15	0.05	
7	Kid		0.50	0.10	
8	Kid 1		0.30	0.01	
9	Naked		1.00	0.085	
10	Bogzagan		5.00	0.60	
	Total networks			1.57	
	New Dargom Gulba Hydroelectric Power Station Gauging Station				53.100
	FIK				0.923

Figure 4. Utilization of Water from the Dargom Canal

Conclusion

Hydrometric, morphological, and kinematic characteristics of the Yangi Darg'om Canal were determined based on field measurements, and methods for calculating the canal's efficiency coefficient were presented. Water discharge, flow velocity, canal surface width, and other characteristics were obtained using modern measuring instruments. The technical condition of structures and water intake facilities located along the route of the Yangi Darg'om Canal was studied. It was found that the canal's efficiency has decreased as a result of the deterioration of its concrete lining.

By increasing the efficiency of canals, it is possible to improve water supply for agricultural crops and automate water management processes at water management facilities. This allows for transparent water accounting. Due to global climate change, population growth, economic sector expansion, and the increasing annual demand for water, it is necessary to address the issues of timely delivery of water limits to consumers and mitigation of water demand. This can be achieved by utilizing modern advanced technologies in water metering systems to alleviate the year-on-year water resource scarcity.

References

1. Naloychenko A.O., Atakanov A.Zh. The Application of Basic Water Metering Structures and Technical Means of Standardized Water Distribution for Rational Water Use in Irrigation (2009)
 2. Karasev I. F., Vasiliev A. V., Subbotina E. S., Hydrometry, 1991.
 3. Biryukov B.V., Danilov M.A., Kivilis S.S. Accurate Measurements of Liquid Flow. Moscow: Mashinostroenie, 1977.
 4. Kienchuk A.F. Water Distribution in Irrigation Systems. Kiev: Urozhay, 1989.
 5. Ibragimov I.Y. - Stages of Construction of Various Types of Hydrological Posts, 2008
 6. Sherov, A.G. Water Metering in Small Canals (2016)
 7. Sabinin G.Kh. Dependence of anemometer readings on flow structure - "Journal of Geophysics," 1937, vol. 7, issues 2-3, pp. 164-176.
- Zheleznyakov G.V. Trapezoidal upward-narrowing spillway, "Reports of the Timiryazev Agricultural Academy," 1962, pp. 234-242.

